

Corrosion resistance of biomedical magnesium alloys in simulated body fluids. Application of chitosan coatings.

Halina Krawiec, Iryna Kozina, Maria Starowicz, Magdalena Kawalec

AGH – University of Science and Technology, Faculty of Foundry Engineering,
Reymonta 23 street, 30-059 Krakow, Poland

Corresponding author (H. Krawiec): krawiec@agh.edu.pl

Magnesium and its alloys exhibit low density and high strength-to-weight ratio. In recent years, many studies are devoted to the application of Mg alloys as a new class of biodegradable implant materials. It has been revealed that pure magnesium exhibits very good biocompatibility and its density is close to that of natural bones (1.8 - 2.1 g cm³). However, the low corrosion resistance of magnesium alloys in physiological fluids significantly limits their application in the biomedical sector. In vitro and in vivo studies have shown that magnesium alloys easily undergo resorption and do not cause allergic reactions. Fast corrosion of magnesium alloys is related with the presence of high concentration of chloride ions in the body fluids. In order to improve the corrosion resistance of Mg alloys and to hinder their dissolution in physiological fluids, it is necessary to perform surface treatment (coatings, laser treatment...).

In this work, the corrosion behaviour of several magnesium alloys (Mg₂₀Zn and Mg₁₉Zn₁Ca) have been investigated in the Hank's solution at 37 °C. In order to improve the corrosion resistance of Mg alloys, protective chitosan coatings were deposited by means of spin coater. The following types of coatings were deposited on the surface of Mg alloys: chitosan, chitosan containing TiO₂ nanoparticles and chitosan with addition of NaF and glass silica. Chitosan is a biodegradable polymer which is safe for health. The electrochemical performance of coated magnesium alloys was evaluated by linear sweep voltamperometry (LSV) and electrochemical impedance spectroscopy. The structure of coatings has been investigated by using Fourier – Transform Infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy. The corrosion tests have revealed that the chitosan coating improves the corrosion resistance of magnesium alloys in simulated body fluids. The highest corrosion resistance of Mg alloys was found when the chitosan coatings containing NaF and Na₂SiO₃ salts were deposited on their surface.

Acknowledgements

The authors would like to thanks to European Commission for financial support in the frame of project H2020-MSCA-ITN-2017, grant agreement no. 764977 –mCBEEs.